

Complexities of Love in the Short Stories of D. H. Lawrence and Ali Smith

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Love has been a very popular subject and theme for literary texts, particularly since the Renaissance in England, when this nation became a nest of singing birds. Love songs, sonnets, sonnet sequences, longer poems, and plays were written aplenty by some of the greatest poetic minds, such as Shakespeare, Spenser, Sir Philip Sydney, Ben Jonson, and their other contemporaries. Shakespeare can be considered a touchstone for any text that takes up love as its theme. Shakespeare's vast corpus has revealed several faces of love. The short stories of D. H. Lawrence and Ali Smith have dealt with the idea of love in a nuanced way, which certainly needs the attention of scholars. The present paper focusses on: (a) what two short story writers after Shakespeare have made of love and (b) how women's movements have liberated individuals, as is revealed in the two literary texts.

Love turns out to be a highly complex emotion, tending to betray anyone who tries to chart its nature through experimentation or textual analysis. Yet, it may not be incorrect to assume that the best accounts of the nature of love are contained in literary texts. D. H. Lawrence and Ali Smith are both powerful authors whose texts reveal that they can virtually "see into the life of things." A point of comparison between Lawrence and Smith arises out of the fact that both of them were interested in same-sex love. About Lawrence, we know very little on the subject, except perhaps what emerges from a statement or two made by Frieda Weekley and his own letters written to different people. Regarding Frieda's exposé on Lawrence's homosexuality, Frances Wilson notes:

. . . one such mishap, Frieda told Mabel, had been Lawrence's affair with a young Cornish farmer during the war. Frieda had similarly warned off H.D. by telling her that Lawrence was homosexual." (p. 368)

Lawrence's letters also show his curiosity towards homosexuality. In one such letter written to Henry Savage in 1913, he writes, "I should like to know why nearly every man that approaches greatness tends to homosexuality, whether he admits it or not . . ." (The Letters of D. H. Lawrence, Volume II, 1913-16, 115). Another instance of his interest in same-sex relationships is seen when he says, "I believe the nearest I've come to perfect love was with a young coal-miner when I was about 16" (MacKenzie, pp. 167-168). In his letter to John Middleton Murry, he expresses his desire to have a blood-brother relationship with Murry and live thereafter with him on an island called Rananim. In that letter, he wrote to John Middleton Murry and Katherine Mansfield:

. . . he felt that they were his only real friends in the world, and urged them to join him and Frieda in Cornwall, even sketching for them detailed diagrams of a cottage he had found for

them: “It would be so splendid . . . such a lovely place: our Rananim” And he was talking of a mystic blood-brotherhood: “No more quarrels and quibbles. Let it be agreed for ever. I am Blutbrüder: Blutbrüderschaft between us all” (Griffin, 78)

In the case of Ali Smith, who comes later than Lawrence, it is rather easy to speak with confidence about one’s sexuality without the fear of disgrace. The comparison made between the two authors in this paper will be text-based; the two stories under focus will be “The Horse Dealer’s Daughter” by D. H. Lawrence and “Free Love” by Ali Smith.

There is this obvious similarity of same-sex love in the two authors in this paper, but there are dissimilarities that keep them apart. Together these two short stories could be set to contain a rather holistic picture of love, the one story complementing the other. “The Horse Dealer’s Daughter” does not show any direct effects of the war and was collected in 1922 in a volume called *England, My England and Other Stories*. Lawrence’s story contains a significant documentation of the status of women at the time when it was written. This story shows very clearly that Mabel Pervin’s three brothers, even though they are in the same economic plight as her, are much more confident than her. Even though love is so central a theme in Lawrence, its physical anatomy is reported directly to the reader all the time. Somewhere in his subconscious, Lawrence seems to relate love with economics. It is as though free love will come together with a free-flowing income. In “The Horse Dealer’s Daughter,” the woman is left without an income after her father dies and his business winds up. A woman seems rather dependent—on a father, brother, or son—to live comfortably without fear or favour. In the years on both sides of 1920, women rarely stepped out into the world, as it was common and well-accepted practice to keep them back under the security of a man. Virginia Woolf does write rather with certitude that in order to write, a woman needs money and a room of her own. She writes this perhaps because women were often not in possession of much money unless they came into an inheritance. This is what Woolf writes. “. . . a woman must have money and a room of her own if she is to write fiction; and that . . . leaves the great problem of the true nature of woman and the true nature of fiction unsolved” (pp. 7-8). *A Room of One’s Own* was published in the same decade as Lawrence’s story and can be said to contain something of the freedom of women enjoyed in that decade.

Both the stories under discussion suggest that money, and its earnings, affects love relationships. Lawrence’s woman protagonist, Mabel Pervin, is a very accurate portrait of how much her life and its independence depend on her economic status. She is reduced to a silent presence after the death of her mother. Her situation worsens when her father marries another woman and becomes one of desperation when her father dies. Each of her three brothers is going his own way when the story begins because the finances of the family will not allow them to stay together anymore. Mabel has grown into a “sullen-looking young woman of twenty-seven” (“Horse Dealer’s Daughter,” 225). The difference between the rights and privileges of men and women has been described by Lawrence in the sentence, “She did not share the same life as her brothers. She would have been good-looking, save the impassive fixity of her face, “bull-dog,” as her brothers called it” (225). Her looks and her sullenness have resulted from a bleak future that seems to surround her. In this situation, love was one of the very few things that could sustain a woman of that time. Love for Lawrence was not unaccompanied by sex. For him, as for few writers, to catch love by the nose, one needed to examine the nature of the sexual relationship. It

was as though love, particularly between a man and a woman, rarely existed without sex. In Ali Smith's story, once again it is the economics of the matter that is largely responsible for love to be possible; love with her too is not unaccompanied by sex. Smith has moved ahead of the modernist position in Lawrence, when a woman was so dependent on a man for her social status. In the postmodern situation, a woman is much more independent and indeed self-dependent in both lesbian and heterosexual love. Unlike Mabel Pervin, who has experienced an attraction and love for Jack Fergusson, the unnamed narrator in "Free Love" is free to love a woman and then another if she so desires. Interestingly, the protagonist of Smith's story visits a prostitute and gets what she considers some of her happiest moments in love. The prostitute, Suzi, has made her love available, at a payment, to both men and women. But in a sense, Smith seems to suggest the prostitute is superior to other women, particularly to her other girlfriend, Jackie, because she offers pure love free of cost, at least the first time, and then leaves it to her customer to partake of her love after a fee that she demands. The difference between the narrator in "Free Love" and the protagonist of Lawrence's story is that Smith's narrator is economically in a sound position, capable of buying love. Lawrence's woman, Mabel, is in the throes of penury and has decided to end her life by drowning in a pond in the absence of an economically sound existence. Mabel has to almost plead to get Dr. Jack Fergusson's love. The repetition of her near-pleading tone is significant to understand this aspect of her situation:

'Do you love me then?' she asked.

'You love me,' she murmured, in strange transport, yearning and triumphant and confident. 'You love me. I know you love me, I know.' (242)

Her repeated query to Dr. Jack Fergusson that goes on for at least the next three or four pages is replied to by the doctor in two parts. In the first barrage of questions relating to whether he loves her, he replies that he does not. It is merely his profession as a doctor that requires him to save lives, even from drowning, and once out of the pond from dying of suffocation, Mabel has to cling to the man bodily to arouse his sexual instincts, which will then lead to love. For Lawrence, as for Smith, love can be synonymous with sexual attraction leading to a sexual act. He believed in the holiness of sex, as his novel *The Rainbow* demonstrates in the case of Anton and Ursula. Lawrence seems to suggest that if a couple is on the verge of a break-up, sex is a good way of making it up and getting into a fine relationship again. In the second part of Fergusson's response to her repeated questioning, Fergusson has come to love her. It is a milder version of a kind of seduction for which Thomas Hardy's men are so blamed in a novel like *Tess of the d'Urbervilles: A Pure Woman Faithfully Presented*. From what emerges in Lawrence's story, love can be coaxed out of another through word and deed. Repeated requests can melt a stubborn man. Sex, in every case, is the final sign or an indication that love exists between two individuals. Plato seems totally absent from this scene. It seems as if the idea of platonic love finds itself in a discomfiting position in the works of Lawrence.

In Smith's story too, sex is essential but does not seem to be the basic unit of love. She makes a distinction between the narrator's two visits to the same prostitute, Suzi, one of which is described as love-giving to a greater extent than the other. In the second visit, the narrator has had to make her payment, which she makes happily. The second visit can be compared to the love relationship between Mabel and Jack Fergusson because Mabel needs this man to survive. If he loves her, he would probably marry her or at least provide for her, being the kind of man he

is. Mabel's love results from constant pleading and coaxing, not like the love between the prostitute and the narrator of "Free Love" in their first meeting. In both the stories, economics, then, has a vital role to play in love relationships.

Literature is a record of the social order, social structure, the roles that people play in society, and the accruing social statuses they acquire. The two short stories under consideration can be seen to reflect the changing social statuses and the freedom women enjoyed in the early twentieth century as opposed to what they enjoyed in its last decade. In this period of seventy to eighty-odd years, much had changed for women in society because between the two, the feminist movement had acquired its legs to stand on. The narrator in "Free Love" seems to have the same kind of independence as enjoyed by men: the freedom to go where she wants and to do what she wants. She does not have to worry much about the number of love relationships she has or the number of men she sleeps with. She can write about all her sexual encounters without fear of social disgrace. Feminism has helped women to become individuals and to be self-dependent. With the help of feminism, the number of barriers put in their way by society has been substantially reduced. Feminism has facilitated women with the agency to be as promiscuous and adulterous as men. In the case of the woman narrator in Smith's story, she is unmarried and has therefore even more freedom. Today, women have been able to do away with marriage, and a number of them live in peace, without having to constantly undergo the societal scrutiny for staying a spinster, to a very large extent. The institution of marriage seems to have lost some of its charm. The feminist critic Irene G. Dash writes about how marriage demands more of women than men:

The regulations that limit a woman's activity in marriage are greater than those limiting a man's; despite the advantages of security and protection that marriage assures her, the woman actually loses more and gains less than does the man, reasons the late nineteenth-century sociologist, Emile Durkheim. John Stuart Mill denounces the relationship because "it confers upon one of the parties to the contract, legal power and control over the person, property, and freedom of action of the other party, independent of her own wishes." (pp. 103-104)

Both Mill and Durkheim lived before D. H. Lawrence wrote "The Horse Dealer's Daughter." Their views could have more significance for him than for Ali Smith, who came several decades later. Even without marriage, with a hope of marrying for the sake of security, Mabel seems almost on her knees before her prospective husband, whose love would not be that easy to procure. In contrast to Mabel's predicament in love, the woman narrator in Smith's story indeed has freedom in love, and the title of the story, "Free Love," is well chosen. In Lawrence's story, the woman protagonist is shown as a man's daughter lacking in an independent identity; the story has almost no role for her father because he is dead before it has begun. But his presence has lived on to provide hurdles in the way of Mabel Pervin's independent existence. D. H. Lawrence, in his essay "Give Her a Pattern" (1929), argues that women will do well only if they are provided with a program or pattern by a man:

The real trouble about women is that they must always go on to adapt themselves to men's theories of women, as they always have done. When a woman is thoroughly herself, she is being what her type of man wants her to be. When a woman is hysterical it's because she doesn't quite know what to be, which pattern to follow, which man's picture of woman to live up to. (p. 160)

Mabel seems to be close to reaching that position when she will look to Jack Fergusson to give her a pattern. There is very little independence in her. She was a certain man's daughter till such time as she was saved by another man. First, one man gave her a pattern, and now she is desperate to get another pattern from another man. The desperation in her words, when she asks him whether or not he loves her, is indicative of the dependence of women on men. Praise be to feminism for liberating women and giving them that freedom, which is visible in a number of woman characters created by Ali Smith. The love of Mabel would come at a certain cost: a kind of submission to a man after which she will again be dependent on him, never as free as the women in Ali Smith's world.

To begin with, Mabel has been brought up in the home of a fairly well-to-do man, a horse dealer who does not seem to be lacking in basic comforts. It is different that now she has her fortunes changed. Her values and mindset were nurtured in a household of prosperity. Her economic problems are a recent development. The shackles of her mind have been created in a male-dominated society, one in which man was independent and woman was not. If she was, then she was independent with reservations, as Lady Chatterley is because of a crippled husband. Her love with another man is managed in hiding, not in an open situation. Feminism has been a very positive movement and has come as a boon for the open-minded and freedom-loving woman. It can be described as one of the best movements that have come about after the intellectual ideas generated by the French Revolution. In the absence of a movement like feminism, it is difficult to think that a woman writer beginning her short story as Ali Smith does in "Free Love":

The first time I ever made love with anyone it was with a prostitute in Amsterdam. I was eighteen and her name was Suzi, I don't think she was much older than I was. I had been cycling round the town in a bad mood and had come upon the red light district quite by chance; it was the most pleasant red light district I have ever got lost in. (1)

Smith's story is evidence of the freedom women enjoy now. This is a freedom where men can happily be excluded from the lives of the women, never imposing their wills upon them. The following passage reveals this newfound freedom:

I come from a small town; one night my friend Jackie [woman] and I had been sitting in a pub and two girls had been sitting at a table on the other side of the room; they looked conventional, more so than we did really, they had long hair, were wearing a lot of make-up, and it was when I glanced to see what kind of footwear they had on that I noticed one of them had one foot out of her high-heeled shoe and was running it up and down the other one's shin under the table. (pp. 2-3)

Smith's story reveals women in states of exhilaration as well as less excited states in the contemporary world. The women in this story are definitely out of the clutches of a man-dominated world. There are references to conventional behaviour, but these are not of a pressing need. Reading Lawrence's story first and then Smith's shows the difference that particular societies have on particular individuals.

In the beginning of this article, it was said that Shakespeare can be a touchstone for authors that write about love. His sonnets, written in the tradition of Petrarch, speak of an undying and unwavering love. Some of his plays, like *Macbeth*, *Othello*, and *Antony and Cleopatra*—where one gets a glimpse of what happens after marriage—reveal suffering and tragedy. In *Antony and Cleopatra*, Antony’s relationship with two of his wives is rather painful because there is no love in them. With *Cleopatra*, there is love because they are unmarried. The world of the comedies seems a happy one because it ends in marriage, and we never get to know what happens thereafter. If we look at the relationship between love and marriage in Shakespearean tragedies and comedies, one can easily opine that marriage is not a great source of happiness. Shakespeare could see as a contemporary author like Ali Smith does. These authors seem to suggest that marriage is an impediment in the way of happiness. Marriage takes away “free love” and gives to the partners a bonding that probably has comfort and love for some time and thereafter a life without that uninterrupted comfort and love.

The texts of these three literary authors seem to point in the same direction: that in a traditionally male-dominated society, love is not easy to come by, and if it does come along with marriage, it comes with attached problems—problems that weaken both the partners. It seems as if these writers suggest that marriage chokes love.

Shakespeare’s women—Portia, Lady Macbeth, and Cleopatra particularly—are much ahead of their times and are rather independent to do as they like, having their own way in whatever they do—both with their own men and the world outside. Shakespeare’s women, such as Rosalind, Viola, and some others, also manage to attract other women; Rosalind attracts Celia, and Viola attracts Olivia. But they have the added dimension of attracting men in men’s disguise; Rosalind dressed as Ganymede can attract Orlando, and Olivia dressed as Cesario can attract Duke Orsino. Shakespeare seems to have more faces of love and differently structured gender roles performed by his women characters. There are more transgender positions in Shakespeare than in later authors, which shows how Shakespeare’s mind approached gender and sexuality. D. H. Lawrence was a rather forward-looking author of his time, and yet he rarely created same-sex characters in his literary texts. Ursula Brangwen’s attraction towards her teacher, Winifred Inger, in *The Rainbow* and Gerald Crich’s attraction towards Rupert Birkin in *Women in Love* are rather the exception than the rule. In *Women in Love*, there is an intimate depiction of a same-sex encounter when Gerald and Rupert have a jujutsu bout naked. However, Lawrence never shows same-sex relationships as the central themes of his novels or stories. He seems hesitant to do that in spite of the details he goes through to describe heterosexual love. “The Horse Dealer’s Daughter” can be considered what Lawrence was comfortable with even though it does not describe the lovers in the act as lovers in other texts are. Lawrence, in spite of his avant-garde position in modernist writing, is still a traditionalist very largely where love is concerned. It is for this reason that F. R. Leavis considers Lawrence to be one of those writers who affirm life rather than negate it. His sexual themes, too, seem to support life in the ultimate analysis. Lawrence’s positive views towards life are reflected in F. R. Leavis’s observation: But it was not in Lawrence’s nature to rest in negation. He was acquainted with horror and foreboding and a state bordering on despair, but it was not possible for him to be defeatist. The affirmation of life was always strong in him, and he had always that profound responsibility which, whatever one may conclude about some of its manifestations, is of his strength and his genius. (32)

What is so fresh and likeable in Ali Smith's story is her uninhibitedness on the subject of sexual love. It seems to fall in line with certain contentions of Judith Butler regarding her performativity theory of gender. In her 1999 preface to *Gender Trouble*, Judith Butler writes:

What continues to concern me most is the following kinds of questions: what will and will not constitute an intelligible life, and how do presumptions about normative gender and sexuality determine in advance what will qualify as the "human" and the "livable"? In other words, how do normative gender presumptions work to delimit the very field of description that we have for the human? What is the means by which we come to see this delimiting power, and what are the means by which we transform it? (xxii)

Because of the new directions given to gender theory, particularly by Butler's term "gender performativity," a writer such as Ali Smith, whether she has or has not acquainted herself with Butler, as an author of contemporary times has understood what it is that "will qualify as the 'human' and the 'livable'" (*Gender Trouble*, xxii). "Free Love" is a woman's reveling in the freedom that the contemporary world confers upon her. There is little self-consciousness in her narrative either when the narrator speaks of going to Suzi, a prostitute, or when she talks of having learned the art of sex with Suzi and then trying to use it with Jackie. Smith's narrator is the epitome of contemporary womanhood. She does not feel shy of describing the savage, cruel thoughts that come to her in her relationship with her best friend:

Nothing could spoil my holiday after that, I didn't care anymore. And that's when Jackie started being unusually nice to me; this was confusing because although we were best friends we were pretty horrible to each other most of the time. (6)

"Free Love" is a story that reflects how simple and easy it is for people to get out of relationships, as the narrator gets out of her relationship with Jackie after it has matured. Gone are those chains that kept people trapped in bad relationships and marriages. Because of the economic status of some women, they can walk out of an unpleasant relationship without being guilty because the structure of society has changed from what it must have been when Lawrence wrote. Lesbian relationships are still probably not what most of the people accept as natural. Yet, the freedom with which Smith describes their lesbian acts may have some social condemnation in the background, but they can still be discussed without inhibition. Here is an example: The first place we really made love was arriving back home after Amsterdam in the women's toilets at the bus station, hands inside clothes, pushed up against the wall and the locked door in the minutes before her father was due to come and take us and our rucksacks home. It was one of the most exciting things I have ever done in my life, though Jackie always called it our sordid first experience. . . . We both had a lot of denying to do and that's something that certainly brought us closer together at the time. We had to thank them [some people who observed these two making love publicly] for. Recently Jackie and I lived in the same city again for a while, and we were always nice to each other when we'd meet occasionally in the street. We both know we owe each other that, at least. (pp. 8-9)

Considering the time in which Lawrence was writing, it was only obvious for him to contain his innermost drives towards homosexuality. More so when his work, *The Rainbow*, was censored and 1,011 copies of it were seized and burnt after an obscenity trial in 1915. The novel became

unavailable in Britain for 11 years (McNally Jackson Independent Booksellers). Ali Smith writes at a time when the feminist movement has already given voice to the suppressed women's desires.

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